

A Study on Planning and Decision Making Ability of Rural Women Entrepreneurs in Dindigul District, Tamil Nadu

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P. Manickam

*Ph.D. Full Time Research Scholar, Department of Management Studies
Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai*

Dr. M. Premkumar

*Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies
Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai*

Abstract

The study was conducted to know the planning and decision making behavior of rural women entrepreneurs in Dindigul district. The women in the district are engaged in various kinds of economic activities which gradually empower them in different aspects. The planning and decision making abilities are the prominent qualities of an entrepreneur. The entrepreneurial activities of the women are confined to the local area and development of enterprises is largely influenced by age. The study revealed that the income activity available in the local area is not directly related to the age of the respondents. Moreover, the relationship between advice from experts and experience person for planning the economic activities and are non-existed. The planning ability of the respondents is not influence by the age. The educational qualification and adoption of new enterprises of the women respondents' shows negative relationship. Therefore, the study suggested that the well-defined training and practices of success strategies of experts are the solution to overcome the initial problems of women entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial behavior, Planning, Decision Making, Women Entrepreneurs.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is one of the most important factors contributing to the economic growth of the society. The entrepreneurs are persons of any country for promoting economic growth and technological creativity change in the society. The growth of entrepreneurship is directly related to the socio-economic growth of the society. Entrepreneurship is the capacity for innovations and dexterity to start creative techniques in business operations. Entrepreneurship contributes to multidimensional growth in several ways - assembling and harnessing various inputs bearing the risks; innovating and imitating the techniques of production to reduce the cost and increase its quality and quantity. Expanding the horizons of the market and coordinating and managing the manufacturing unit at various

levels to develop in the society. Entrepreneur is a person who has an to do create something new, organize production, undertake high risks and handle the economic uncertainty involved in running an enterprise. Whatever be the definition, entrepreneurs have been considered as instrumental in initiating and sustaining socio-economic growth. The growth of women entrepreneurs has results in socio-economic uplift of deprived class and vast employment creation. Women entrepreneurs are assisted by the government for startup fund and provided training. Though, the planning and decision making abilities are important for the success of the business.

Objectives of the Study

The Major objectives of the study are given below-

- To understand the socio-economic status of rural women entrepreneurs.
- To analyze the planning ability of rural women entrepreneurs
- To analyze decision making ability of rural women entrepreneurs

Hypotheses

- There is no relationship between concern of income activity in the local area and age.
- There is no relationship between age and advice from experts and experienced person for planning the economic activities of the women respondents.
- There is no relationship between education and adoption of new enterprises of the women respondents
- There is no relationship between education and place for establishment enterprises of the women respondents.

Methodology

The present study is entirely based on primary data sources. The primary data were collected through a well structure interview schedule. A sample size of 120 rural women respondent was selected from the rural regions of Dindigul district. The researcher has visited the firm directly and met the entrepreneur. The simple percentage method and chi-square test were used to analyze the data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The collected data were processed with the help of SPSS and tabulated. The final results are presented below. The study has two major parts- the first part deals with socio-economic condition of the respondents and the second part covers the planning and decision making abilities of the respondent.

Table 1 Age -wise distribution of respondents

S.No	Age Group	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1.	Below 20Years	37	30.8
2.	21 to 30Years	42	35
3.	31 to 40 Years	35	29.2
4.	Above 41 Years	6	5
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

Table 1 shows the age-wise distribution of respondents. Among the overall 120 respondents, 42 (35%) respondents belong to the age category of 21 to 30 years. This is followed by 37 (30.8%)

respondents belong to age category of below 20 years, 35 (29.2%) respondents belong to age category 31 to 40 years and 6 (5%) respondents belong to age category above 41 years. Hence, most of the respondents belong to the category of age 21 to 30 Years.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents by Education- wise

S.No	Education	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1.	Up to SSLC	17	14.2
2.	HSC	16	13.3
	UG	38	31.7
3.	PG	6	5
4.	Professional Course	43	35.8
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents by educational qualifications. It is found from the table that 35.8% of the respondents qualified professional course followed by 31.7% of respondents studies pounder graduate degree, 14.2% of respondents studied up to SSLC (Secondary School Leaving Certificate), 13.3% of the respondents had education up to HSC and 5% of the respondents did Post Graduate degree.

Table 3 Distribution of respondents by Martial states - wise

S.No	Martial states	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1.	Married	47	39.2
2.	Un Married	63	52.5
3.	Widow	10	8.3
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents by marital status. In this study, 63 (52.5%) of the respondents were unmarried, 47 (39.2%) of the respondents were married and rest 10 (8.3%) of the respondents were widow.

Table 4 Distribution of respondents by Family size -wise

S.No	Income in Rs.	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1.	Up to 3	60	50
2.	4 to 5	40	33.3
3.	Above 6	20	16.7
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

Tables 4 reveal the distribution respondents by family size. Among the respondents, the majority (50%) of the respondents' have family size up to 3, and it is followed by 40 respondents (33.3%) have family size of 4 to 5 and 20 respondents (16.7%) have family size Above 6 respectively.

Table 5 Distribution of respondents by Income-wise

S.No	Income in Rs.	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1.	Up 10000	66	55
2.	11000 to 15000	26	21.7
3.	16000 to 20000	11	9.2
4.	Above 21000	17	14.2
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

Among the 120 respondents, a majority of the (55%) respondents' have income level up to Rs. 10000, and followed by 26 respondents (21.7%) have income between Rs.11000 and 15000, 17 respondents (9.2%) have income more than Rs.16000 to 20000 and 17 respondents (14.2%) have income above 21000 respectively.

Table 6 Distribution of respondents by Type of Business

S.No	Type of Business	No. of. Respondents	Percentage
1.	Tea Shop	19	15.8
2.	Flower & Vegetable Shop	14	11.7
3.	Retail And Grocery	27	22.5
4.	Hand Craft	15	12.5
5.	Xerox And Printing	25	20.8
6.	Beauty Pallor	13	10.8
7.	Others	7	5.8
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary data

It is inferred from the table 6 that about a quarter of the respondents owned retail and grocery shop, 15.8 percent owned tea shop, 11.7 percent have flower and vegetable shop, 12.5 percent have handcraft shop, 20.8 percent have Xerox and printing shop, 10.8 percent have beauty parlor and remaining 5.8 percent have other businesses. It is evident that retail and grocery and Xerox and printing are the most preferable business by the women in the rural area.

Table 7 Planning abilityof the women entrepreneurs

S. No	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
1	The income activity available to their local area is the only concern than extending the unit to other areas.	62(51.7)	38(31.7)	15(12.5)	3(2.5)	2(1.7)	120
2	The amount for purchasing inputs should be assessed in advance.	13(10.8)	82(68.3)	13(10.8)	5(4.2)	7(5.8)	120
3	The initial cost of starting income generating activity is not a concern	18(15.0)	54(45.0)	45(37.5)	0	3(2.5)	120

4	The prior decision about the step of economic activity is very important.	19(15.8)	35(29.2)	36(30.2)	19(15.8)	11(9.2)	120
5	Advice from experts and experienced persons for planning the economic activities is necessary.	24(20.0)	15(12.5)	26(21.7)	42(35.0)	13(10.8)	120
6	Production plans is the way to increase return.	12(10.0)	50(41.7)	16(13.3)	32(26.7)	10(8.3)	120

It is evident from the table that a little more than fifty percent of the respondents strongly agreed that the income activity available to their local area is the only concern than extending the unit to other areas. There were only 1.7 percent strongly disagree with this. The majority of the respondents agreed that the amount for purchasing inputs should be assessed in advance. The respondents disagreed this statement was very meager. Only 15 percent of the respondents strongly agreed that the initial cost of starting income generating activity is not a concern whereas more than fifty percent of the respondents agreed to this. A large number of respondents disagree that the advice from experts and experienced persons for planning economic activities is necessary. It is found that about half of the respondents agreed that the new production plans are the way to increase return whereas, 8.3 percent strongly disagree with this. It is obvious from the study that the large concern of the women entrepreneurs is to gain income from the local areas.

Table 8 Decision making ability of the women entrepreneurs

S. No	Statement	Not Considered	Considered after consultation with others	Decision taking Independently	Total
1	Adoption of new enterprises.	71(59.2)	31(25.8)	18(15)	120
2	Planning of establishment of enterprise.	27(22.5)	71(59.2)	22(8.3)	120
3	Amount & lend of money for inputs.	35(29.2)	53(44.2)	32(26.7)	120
4	Place for establishment of enterprise.	15(12.5)	75(62.5)	30(25.0)	120
5	Amount of produce in earlier days.	33(27.5)	25(20.8)	62(51.2)	120
6	Determination of the price of produce.	29(24.2)	60(50.0)	31(25.8)	120
7	Transporting by which mode.	26(21.7)	67(55.8)	27(22.5)	120
8	Selling at local market or others.	39(32.5)	55(45.8)	26(21.7)	120
9	Managing the unit.	50(41.7)	43(35.8)	27(22.5)	120

The decision making ability of the women entrepreneurs made it clear that the adoption of new enterprises is not a consideration of majority of respondents in the study. About 60 percent of the respondents opined that planning of establishment of enterprise would consider after consultation with others. Moreover, the decision of amount & lend of money for inputs and place for establishment of enterprise are consider after consultation with others. Their respective percentages

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are 44.2 percent and 62.5 percent. There were 51.2 percent opined that the amount of produce in earlier days was decided by independently. The determination of the price of produce, the mode of transportation and place of selling the product are decided after consultation with others. The management of the unit is not considered by majority of the respondents in the study. Chi-Square Test was used to test the hypotheses. The result of the test is presented below.

H0:There is no relationship between concern of income activity in the local area and age.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Peason Chi-Square	28.8	12	.0004
Likehihood Ratio	32.342	12	.001
Kubear-by-linear association	2.155	1	.142
N of valid cases	120		

5 percent Level of significance

The calculated value is 28.88, which is higher than table value 18.5476. Therefore, null hypothesis will be rejected. The income activity available in the local area is not directly related to the age of the respondents. H0:There is no relationship between age and advice from experts and experience person for planning the economic activities of the women respondents.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Peason Chi-Square	57.835	12	.000
Likehihood Ratio	60.468	12	.000
Kubear-by-linear association	.541	1	.462
N of valid cases	120		

Level of significant at 5%

The calculated value is 57.835, which is higher than table value 18.5476. There is no relationship between age and advice from experts and experience person for planning the economic activities of the women respondents. H0:There is no relationship between education and adoption of new enterprises of the women respondents

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Peason Chi-Square	51.305	8	.000
Likehihood Ratio	61.521	8	.000
Kubear-by-linear association	.817	1	.366
N of valid cases	120		

The calculated value is 51.305, which is higher than p value (.000). There is no relationship between education and adoption of new enterprises of the women respondents. H0:There is no relationship between education and place for establishment enterprises of the women respondents.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Peason Chi-Square	72.206	8	.000
Likehihood Ratio	65.174	8	.000
Kubear-by-linear association	26.518	1	.000
N of valid cases	120		

The calculated value is 72.206, which is higher than p value (.000). There is no relationship between education and place for establishment enterprises of the women respondents.

Suggestions

The following suggestions are made to enhance the process of planning and decision making abilities of women entrepreneurs.

- The marketing of the products of women entrepreneurs confined to the particular region that limit the prospects of higher profit. Therefore, the involvement of cooperative society and government for expanding the market will increase the income.
- Majority of the respondents in the study are not consulting any expert for planning and decision making. Therefore, practical knowledge and innovative ideas lacks. In order to overcome this, skill training and advance classes on modern business practices are the need of the hour.
- The problems such as lack of space to store of products, absence of credit and shortage of raw materials should be addressed through collective effort of government and entrepreneur's society to strengthen the performance.

Conclusion

The role of women in the society has been changing time to time. The entrepreneurial role of women has much addressed in government policies and initiatives for women entrepreneurship development has made. The higher educational attainment and favourable policies on the part of administration has accelerated the growth of women entrepreneurs. The experience in the field of work and educational attainment has helped them to take decision in any difficult situation. The study proved that the decision making ability of the rural women entrepreneurs in Dindigul is very poor and in most cases they depends on the opinion of the experts. The planning ability of the rural women entrepreneurs in different situations is not much sound. Therefore, an imitative is required on the administrative level to train them properly to sustain the women participation in the business.

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